

University Marine Energy Research Community

2023 Conference

4-6 October | Durham, NH, USA

A Case Study on Powering the Blue Economy through Hydrogen-Powered Coastal Maritime Transportation

Saffeer M. Khan, Jeffrey Knollmeyer, Himanshu Chavan, Prithwiraj Roy Chowdhury

University of North Carolina at Charlotte, 9201 University City Blvd, Charlotte, NC-28223, USA

Abstract

This paper presents a case study on the feasibility of hydrogen fuel cells for North Carolina ferry fleet. DOE's Powering the Blue Economy Report has identified renewable hydrogen-powered coastal maritime transportation as an opportunity to cut greenhouse gas emissions to meet federal and state decarbonization goals. The European Marine Energy Center has demonstrated that hydrogen produced with unused marine renewable energy can be stored, transported, and used for maritime and land transportation applications on the Orkney Island. The project team has collected first-hand data on the current state of the NC DOT ferry fleet operating along the Outer Banks and profiles of their daily operations. Part of our data collection included an in-depth case study on the Aurora to Bayview route. The team was able to gather speed profiles of a one-way voyage of each route, tour and measure the engine rooms and fuel tank rooms on two ferries, and interview the ferry crews and DOT engineers. The one-way voyage is representative of each ferry's trips across the Pamlico River, as the ferries are double-ended. The collected data guided the specific placement of the hydrogen fuel cells, electric motors, and hydrogen storage tanks on the ferries. Knowing the current installed power provided a baseline for the power necessary from hydrogen fuel cells, and guided the analysis of the commercially-available options. The team also calculated the CO₂ and NO_x reductions expected from transitioning to hydrogen fuel cell power, and conducted a techno-economic analysis of producing hydrogen at the prevailing electricity rate. As the method of hydrogen production greatly affects the life-cycle emissions impact of using hydrogen as a fuel, the team considered the use of marine renewable energy to power an electrolyzer facility to produce hydrogen for coastal maritime transportation as well as other powering the blue economy applications along the natural disaster-prone coastal communities of North Carolina.

Keywords: Marine renewable energy; Hydrogen fuel cells; Blue economy application; Techno-economic analysis; Coastal maritime transportation; Decarbonization.

1. Introduction

The United States Department of Energy (DOE) has placed a major focus on hydrogen as part of the solution to the energy challenges for meeting the decarbonization goals. North Carolina has set a goal of 70% reduction in carbon emissions by the year 2030 and carbon neutrality by 2050 [1]. Ocean-based sources of renewable energy have the potential to diversify the state's renewable energy portfolio, and can produce hydrogen to power coastal maritime transportation. This zero-emission alternative to existing diesel-based propulsion systems can help achieve the goal of reducing greenhouse gas emissions and decarbonization of economy in line with the objectives of NC Renewable Ocean Energy Program (NCROEP). Energy Production and Infrastructure Center (EPIC) at University of North Carolina Charlotte has been at the forefront of this effort through studies on estimation of power generation profile of offshore marine hydrokinetic (MHK) microgrid clusters, and techno-economic analysis of wind and MHK turbines for electricity, hydrogen production, and water desalination [2]. The impetus from DOE to include hydrogen in the energy economy going forward has only grown since the award of this project a year ago. In September 2022, DOE announced \$7 billion in funding to create regional clean hydrogen hubs (H2Hubs). In March 2023, DOE announced a further \$750 million for research, development, and demonstration efforts to dramatically reduce the cost of clean

hydrogen. The DOE has also released the “U.S. National Clean Hydrogen Strategy and Roadmap” in June 2023, further clarifying the federal government’s intention to widely incorporate hydrogen in daily energy needs.

There have been recent developments on building zero-emissions hydrogen fuel cell vessels to transition the maritime sector to a sustainable future. The vessels use hydrogen fuel cells to power electric propulsion motors and meet the other onboard power needs. There are major economic, technical, and operational challenges in converting the existing fleet vessels to fuel cell power. These include the cost of hydrogen production to meet the energy demands, bunkering infrastructure, onboard storage and handling, safety, installation, integration, maintenance, and regulatory compliance. The existing NC ferry system operates three classes of ferries (Hatteras, River, and Sound) comprising 21 vessels on seven routes transporting more than 800,000 vehicles or approximately 2 million passengers a year and is the second largest state-run ferry system in the United States [3]. The NC ferries have defined routes and points of operation and can be refueled at higher frequency. The fuel cell technologies based on compressed or liquid hydrogen are, therefore, a good candidate for investigation as potential alternative zero-emission power sources. The goal of our project is to provide a holistic look at the technical and economic challenge of converting the NC ferry fleet from existing diesel-based power source to a renewable hydrogen fuel cell system. The team has conducted an extensive study of the use of hydrogen fuel cells on passenger ferries. Sandia National Lab’s work was helpful in our efforts and covered most aspects of marine hydrogen fuel cell use [4-6]. Other works referenced in support of this paper include Pacific Northwest National Laboratory’s Hydrogen (Bi-Directional) online cost and performance estimation tool [7]; the National Renewable Energy Laboratory’s H2A-Lite economic analysis tool [8]; techno-economics of hydrogen compression in [9]; Joint Agency staff report for the California Energy Commission and the California Air Resources Board [10], and work on the refueling cost of hydrogen in [11].

2. Research Approach

The purpose of this project was to investigate the technical and economic feasibility of hydrogen fuel cells to power the NC ferries. This was, largely, a two-sided commission: what are the difficulties in converting the ferries to hydrogen power, and what are the benefits? Answering the former question involved examining the efficiency, complexity, power density, and cost, as well as the installation, integration, testing, operation, maintenance, and safety of commercially-available hydrogen fuel cells in the NC ferries. Also required was a review of the current regulations, rules, and standards by the regulatory organizations related to the use of hydrogen fuel cells on ferries. To answer the latter question, we studied the impact on greenhouse gas emissions of hydrogen fuel cell power systems with those from conventional diesel-based systems.

An important step in the research approach was to collect data on the status quo of the NC ferry fleet in preparation for the subsequent data-gathering visits to the ferries. Some information about the ferry fleet was available through the NCDOT resources [12]. Further data was collected during the team’s trips to the NC Outer Banks. The second trip was particularly fruitful, as the team measured speed profiles of the Cherry Branch to Minnesott Beach, Aurora to Bayview, and Currituck to Knotts Island routes, measured the engine room and diesel storage tanks onboard Governor Daniel Russell ferry (Aurora to Bayview route), and toured the facilities available at each ferry terminal. The team also collected more specific information about the installed engines and generators and the diesel fuel storage by touring the engine room on the. The team collected data to estimate the hydrogen fuel consumption for each route, explore the available hydrogen fuel cell systems that could provide the power needed for each ferry, explore hydrogen fuel storage systems, and estimate the CO₂ and NO_x emissions that could be saved by switching these routes to hydrogen fuel. The team also interviewed the NCDOT employees to ask questions about the vessels, observe operations, and obtain useful fuel usage data.

3. Findings

The literature review provided two significant takeaways - MHK-powered electricity generation with existing technologies is currently economically less competitive off the coast of North Carolina [2], and a hydrogen fuel cell-powered ferry is entirely possible from a physical construction and regulatory standpoint (e.g. Sea Change, a ferry built for use in the San Francisco Bay area powered by a hybrid hydrogen fuel cell and battery system [13]). The status quo of the NC Ferry Fleet is given in Table I. The Ferry Division operates 7 routes using 21 ferries, all of which derive their propulsion power from diesel-fueled internal combustion engines. Figure 1 shows the map of ferry routes along the NC Outer Banks. Broadly, the routes covered by NC Ferry operations can be divided into two categories: shorter and longer crossings. The shorter category includes the routes from Currituck to Knotts Island, Hatteras to Ocracoke,

Route		Crossing Time	Distance	Annual Vehicles	Annual Passengers
Currituck	Knotts Island	45 min.	5.0 miles	30,000	90,000
Hatteras	Ocracoke	1 hr.	8.5 miles	353,000	960,000
Swan Quarter	Ocracoke	2 hrs. 45 min.	27 miles	27,000	65,000
Cedar Island		2 hrs. 15 min.	23 miles	76,000	184,000
Bayview	Aurora	30 min.	3.5 miles	82,000	130,000
Cherry Branch	Minnesott Beach	20 min.	2.5 miles	277,000	487,000
Southport	Fort Fisher	35 min.	3.5 miles	185,000	500,000

Fig. 1. North Carolina Ferry Route Map [5]

Bayview to Aurora, Minnesota Beach to Cherry Branch, and Southport to Fort Fisher (and the reverse of each). The longer category includes two routes, from Ocracoke to Cedar Island, and from Ocracoke to Swan Quarter. The Hatteras to Ocracoke route is somewhat between the two categories in terms of distance and time, and requires a significantly more circuitous route. The routes are largely straight-line voyages from one terminal to another and vice versa. Ocracoke is the only terminal with multiple destinations, as there are three separate ferries emanating from Ocracoke: to Hatteras, to Swan Quarter, and to Cedar Island. The ferries have been built in three classes: the Hatteras, River, and Sound classes. Age of the vessels is an issue for the NCDOT as only one-third of the vessels have been built this century. Ferry production has continued, with the Rodanthe and the Salvo having been completed in the last 4 years. A significant step in our work was gathering speed profiles (speed vs. time) of each route. In addition to providing installed propulsion engine power, it helped the team determine several follow-on items: current diesel fuel consumption, predicted hydrogen fuel consumption (and later costs for both), and an appropriate sizing of the fuel cell and hydrogen fuel storage system. The speed profiles were used to create power profiles, calculate annual diesel fuel consumption, and estimate annual hydrogen fuel consumption for the same service. With the fuel data obtained during the trip to the Cherry Branch ferry terminal, the team compared the estimated fuel volume with that actually used by the ferries in operation on that route. The estimated fuel consumption was 226,738 gallons, while the fuel data indicated an annual consumption of 219,438 gallons (a difference of 7,300 gallons, or 3.3% of the annual consumption indicated by the fuel data).

The fuel consumption estimates for both diesel and hydrogen were used to estimate the fuel costs. For diesel, a price estimate of \$3.691/gal was used. For hydrogen, a cost value was less straightforward and was estimated through the calculation of levelized cost of hydrogen (LCOH) based on PEM electrolysis. Details of this work are omitted due to paucity of space. The estimated LCOH was \$7.836/kg which has been used in this study. The fuel cost estimates indicate diesel-powered ferries currently are the more economical option. Diesel versus Hydrogen Fuel Cost Comparison is given in Table 2. However, the costs for hydrogen fuel is likely to decline significantly in the next decade. USDOE has specifically set a target of reducing the cost of 1 kg of hydrogen fuel to \$1 as announced in June 2021. If realized, this development would result in a reversal of the cost relationship between hydrogen fuel and diesel fuel - hydrogen fuel would then cost 65.8% less than that of diesel.

Hydrogen is a potentially highly beneficial fuel, both because it does not produce any greenhouse gas or particulate pollutant emissions at the point of use and because it is gravimetrically energy dense. However, difficulty arises because hydrogen has very high gravimetric density, but is the least volumetrically dense. The resulting challenge is to find the volume onboard the ferry boats to store the necessary mass of hydrogen. To minimize the volume required per unit mass of fuel, the hydrogen must be compressed to significantly high pressure. Typical storage pressures are 350 or 700 bar. As the entirety of the available weather deck space of the NC ferry boats is used for vehicle capacity, another challenge arises in finding a suitable location above deck for the fuel storage. The follow-on effect of having limited space onboard the vessels for fuel storage comes when selecting the ferry route that is best suited for conversion to hydrogen fuel cell power. The shorter the ferry route, combined with fewer daily crossings, leads to reduced fuel usage, and thus a lesser requirement for onboard fuel storage. Based on this consideration, this study focused on relatively shorter ferry routes along the NC Outer Banks.

Routes	Southport-Fort Fisher	Cherry Branch-Minnesott Beach	Aurora-Bayview			
Diesel Fuel						
Total yearly one-way voyages	10,766	20,440	5,110			
Yearly Fuel Consumption (kg)	664,654.7	729,551.7	310,074.8			
Yearly Fuel Consumption (gal)	206,568.4	226,737.8	96,368.3			
Fuel Cost	\$762,444.01	\$836,889.27	\$355,695.50			
Hydrogen Fuel						
Total yearly one-way voyages	10,766	20,440	5,110			
Yearly Fuel Consumption (kg)	260,853.13	286,322.9	121,755.15			
Pages Fuel Cost	\$2,044,045.11	\$2,243,626.29	\$954,073.35			
H2A Lite Fuel Cost	\$1,139,928.17	\$1,251,231.10	\$532,070.00			
Difference between diesel and H₂ cost	Absolute	%	Absolute	%	Absolute	%
Computed H ₂ Fuel Cost	-\$1,281,601.10	-168.09%	-\$1,406,737.02	-168.09%	-\$598,377.85	-168.23%
H2A Lite Fuel Cost	-\$377,484.16	-49.51%	-\$414,341.83	-49.51%	-\$176,374.50	-49.59%

For optimal operation the onboard storage capacity should be sized such that a ferry can complete an entire day's worth of trips on a single, full fill of fuel. A commercially available storage solution that would work for the shorter routes is the CubePlus 20 Multiple-Element Gaseous Containers (MEGCs) product made by Steelhead Composites. This container is capable of storing 384 kg of hydrogen fuel at 345 bars, with a volumetric footprint of 6.1 m by 2.4 m by 2.9 m (20'x7.9'x9.5'). The hydrogen fuel cell powered ferries which we have previously studied, the hypothetical SF-BREEZE (studied by Sandia National Laboratory) and the in-existence Sea Change have designed and mounted the hydrogen fuel storage on the weather decks, outside of the hull of the vessel. This solution can be implemented on the NC ferries.

The feasible hydrogen fuel cell solutions include the HPM-80 from Genevos (78 kW/module), the FCwave from Ballard (200 kW/module), and the Accelera HyPM-HD45 (45 kW/module). Each of these solutions is scalable and would require an array of modules. Considering a straightforward comparison of the installed propulsion power on most of the River-class ferries (e.g. Governor Daniel Russell) of two 475-hp diesel engines, an equal amount of power would need to be provided, which works out to 710 kW. Thus, a package of ten Genevos HPM-80 modules (with a total volume of 8.96 m³), four Ballard FCwave modules (with a total volume of 7.87 m³), or sixteen Accelera HyPM modules (with a total volume of 1.40 m³) would be sufficient for propulsion alone. Electrical power for the vessel would also need to be considered; this would add an additional 150-200 kW to the power requirement.

A large portion of the motivation of this project is to eliminate the harmful emissions from NC ferry operations. As such, it is important to know how much of an impact can be made by the conversion of the NC ferry fleet from diesel to hydrogen power. The calculated diesel fuel consumption for each route was used to estimate the amount of CO₂ and NO_x emissions from ferry operations that can be reduced by using hydrogen fuel cell power with green hydrogen fuel. The estimation is given in Table 3 and was based on using the U.S. EPA and U.S. Department of Transportation agreed upon value of 10.18 kg of CO₂ produced for every gallon of diesel fuel burned [14], the EIA's energy content of diesel fuel of 137,381 Btu per gallon, and a value of 2.8 lbs NO_x per MMBtu for a similar diesel engine from an EPA study of diesel engine NO_x emissions. Approximating an abatement benefit of eliminating these emissions can be accomplished using the Social Cost of Carbon (SC-CO₂) as defined by the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA). Using the EPA 2020 figures, and an average of the 3% and 2.5% discount rates, gives a value of \$52/metric ton of CO₂ [15]. This results an abatement benefit estimate of \$846,091.

A further consideration is the total fuel cell system cost, including fuel cells, hydrogen storage tanks, electric motors, and all necessary balance of plant components. The team contacted multiple manufacturers of the major components (fuel cells, hydrogen storage solutions, and electric motors) for the cost estimates including Ballard, Genevos, Accelera, Steelhead Composites, Mahytec, BAE Systems, and Wärtsilä. The vendors were willing to provide

cost information only for actual plans and intent to build or retrofit projects. An estimate of the cost of the fuel cells was drawn from the equivalent power to a River-class ferry (approximately 1000 kW), and an estimated fuel cell cost from the SF-BREEZE report of \$2,500/kW [4]. This resulted in a cost of \$2.5 million for the fuel cells. An estimate of the storage cost was obtained from Elliot Bay Design Group’s estimate of \$700/kg of stored hydrogen [6]. With the 384-kg storage capacity of the CubePlus 20 MEGC, this results in a cost of \$268,800. Further work is required to capture the full picture of costs associated with retrofitting the hydrogen fuel cells on NC ferries.

Route	Estimated Annual Diesel Consumption (gal)	Estimated Annual CO ₂ Emissions (kg)	Estimated Annual NO _x Emissions (lb)
Cherry Branch-Minnesott Beach	226,737.81	2,308,190.94	87,218.51
Aurora-Bayview	96,368.33	981,029.59	37,069.70
Currituck-Knotts Island	131,280.68	1,336,437.33	50,499.32
Southport-Fort Fisher	206,568.41	2,102,866.43	79,460.01
Hatteras-Ocracoke	663,745.73	6,756,931.52	255,320.95
Ocracoke-Cedar Island	273,627.97	2,785,532.70	105,255.59
Total	1,598,328.93	16,270,988.51	614,824.07

The team also researched the regulations applicable to hydrogen fuel cell use for marine transportation. Title 46 of the United States Code of Federal Regulations (CFR) provides the applicable regulations for the ferry boats [16]. This code also adopts regulations from section VIII of the ASME Boiler and Pressure Vessel Code [17] and structural standards from the American Bureau of Shipping (ABS) [18]. U.S. Coast Guard (USCG) expert feedback revealed that ABS had released two documents on regulating hydrogen-fueled and fuel cell-powered vessels [19-20]. A USCG expert also stated to the team that “Vessels using H₂ as fuel are currently regulated as vessels of ‘novel design.’” Therefore, the regulatory requirements for converting the existing NC ferry fleet to hydrogen fuel cell power, would require careful design and close coordination with ABS and USCG.

4. Conclusion and Future Work

North Carolina ferry fleet, the second-largest State-operated ferry system behind Washington State, is crucial for the coastal communities. Despite its importance, the fleet is aging, with the oldest vessel being 57 years old. Given the fleet size and significance, it is a prime candidate for decarbonization, either through retrofitting or replacement with hydrogen-powered vessels. Research from Sandia National Laboratory and regulatory guidance from ABS have demonstrated the feasibility of hydrogen-powered ferries. However, the source of hydrogen fuel is critical, with greenhouse gas emissions varying based on production methods. Electrolysis with electricity from ocean renewable energy sources is the ideal option to minimize carbon emissions. Storing hydrogen fuel on current vessels presents challenges, requiring evaluation by NCDOT, ABS, and USCG. While hull storage is unlikely due to safety standards, weather decks are a possibility, albeit with design complexities. The low volumetric density of hydrogen suggests it's best suited for shorter routes. While the environmental benefit of cutting CO₂ emissions is substantial, current hydrogen costs outweigh diesel. Furthermore, North Carolina lacks a significant hydrogen fuel infrastructure which may change with the DOE’s Hydrogen Hub program. For future work to progress, collaboration with NCDOT and participation of their engineering expertise is essential, possibly leading to small-scale demonstration project. Technologies like hydrogen fuel cells, storage, and marine electric motors are mature and reliable. UNC Charlotte’s EPIC has received a grant for the "Clean Carolinas" initiative, focusing on clean energy technology, including marine energy and hydrogen, to boost the regional economy in coastal communities. This paves the way for future innovation and research on use of ocean renewable energy to power electrolyzers and produce hydrogen for coastal maritime transportation and other powering the blue economy applications.

Acknowledgements

The team sincerely appreciates the funding support for this project by the North Carolina Coastal Studies Institute through the North Carolina Renewable Ocean Energy Program. We also acknowledge the mentorship and support of faculty and leadership at the Energy Production and Infrastructure Center, University of North Carolina at Charlotte.

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